

ORGANIZING HISTORY LESSONS BASED ON MODERN APPROACHES AS ONE OF THE KEY PROBLEMS OF TEACHING METHODOLOGY

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Abstract. *This article discusses the current problems of the teaching methodology in educational institutions, the organization of lessons by history teachers based on modern approaches, as well as some issues related to the development of media competence, including educating students in an information society in the context of a competent approach in education, encouraging them to think independently, creativity M. Behbudi's opinions on the possibilities of media education encouraging the development of activities, obtaining information, processing it, summarizing, and drawing conclusions.*

Keywords: *history, information society, independent thought, creative activity, information, media education.*

Nowadays, the organization and transition of lessons based on modern approaches in educational institutions is one of the main urgent problems of the teaching methodology. Because if the teacher is not armed with modern teaching methods and tools, does not understand it or is unable to apply it in practice, this will remain one of the main problems of the teaching methodology.

At this point, it can be mentioned that one of the urgent problems of teaching is to work with information, to analyze it, and to form life skills in them. requirements such as rapid adaptation to the changing modern requirements while continuously improving their skills.

It is also important to study the ideas and views of modern people, to collect, analyze and use information and data in this regard. Also, he interprets M. Behbudi's thoughts and views about the ideas of enlightenment, the need to train national experts for the development of society through the image of an intellectual in his work "Padarkush".

Through the competence approach in education, to teach students to effectively apply the various types of skills they have acquired in the situations encountered in their personal, professional and social lives, together with the acquisition of knowledge, skills and competencies of students in general education subjects in an educational institution, to be able to explain one's opinion to others, to be able to understand them by listening to others, In order to engage in debate, to achieve success in everyday life, it is necessary for the student to search for this information, analyze it, and form the ability to use knowledge, skills and abilities to solve problems encountered in their everyday life. Of course, every teacher does this through his effective lessons. In this regard, especially if education is carried out through media education, the practical result is clearly visible. After all, the competitiveness of pedagogic personnel in educational processes depends on their ability to master advanced educational technologies, and their ability to adapt to changing and increasing professional requirements.

Among the main trends of world development, the transition to an information society is an important task, that is, the influence of media in all aspects of society is considered an urgent problem. On this basis, media competence remains a priority area in continuous professional development of teachers. Because it is permissible to mention the importance of learning a language in the formation of relations and communication with a foreign country in addition to teaching students to find, learn, analyze, and draw conclusions, although M. Behbudi also mentioned that language learning is necessary in his views and is on the agenda. we must mention that he was able to put it.

Therefore, it should be mentioned that the study of M. Behbudi's legacy is important in the development of pedagogy.

At this point, it can be said that the development of information indicators of modern pedagogue's media competence is an important stage of his theoretical preparation for the implementation of media education activities. Typically, educators are media literate and active Internet users. At the same time, there is a problem that most pedagogues struggle to demonstrate their knowledge of media competence: their knowledge of the basic terms of media pedagogy is insufficient, they lack knowledge of the theoretical field of media and media education, media language, the relativity of genres, the main facts of the history of the development of media culture, they have only approximate ideas about the unique aspects of media culture figures.

At a time when many informational threats are trying to have a negative impact on the minds of our youth, it is a very important task to analyze these processes psychologically and find ways to protect our youth from such media threats and implement them. In such conditions, it is necessary to develop media competence taking into account modern requirements, to determine the pedagogical conditions of this process. Currently, in accordance with the requirements of scientific and technical development, it is necessary to define directions for the development of media competence by improving the knowledge of information technologies of students of higher educational institutions.

A competency-based approach to history classes is one that emphasizes learning outcomes. In this case, the result of education is not a collection of acquired information, but the ability of a person to act in various problem situations.

Media competence in history classes is based on innovative educational technologies that depend on creativity to implement innovations today. Media creativity (creativity in the field of media) is a creative ability of a media competent teacher. Media creativity creates an innovative learning environment and leads to the development of media competence.

The purposeful use of information, communication and pedagogical technologies by the teacher in the lesson creates the basis for the students' full mastery of the educational materials related to the subject, as well as opening opportunities such as efficient use of time, perfection, sequence, flexibility, development, large-scale, demonstrability.

The teacher can focus the attention of each student participating in the lesson on the topic, ensure their activity. The use of information and communication technologies in the lesson allows extensive use of electronic textbooks, electronic manuals, additional resources, electronic tasks and multimedia information. In addition to providing students with the opportunity to find the latest sources on the subject and work independently, the Internet creates a foundation for the formation of students' ability to keep up with the times, get to the bottom of each educational material, work independently on sources and information, and make comparative comparisons.

Media education teaches students to think independently, develop creative activities, receive information, process it, summarize, draw conclusions.

In conclusion, it can be said that as a result of the introduction of information and communication technologies, i.e., media education, mobile learning system, to the process of history lessons, the ability to teach young people to work independently, to think freely, and to react to each event is formed. Today, integration of the newest experience products in the field of pedagogy into education is the demand of the time, ensuring its integration with education is the primary task of our pedagogues. After all, M. Behbudi in his work "Padarkush" beautifully expresses his efforts to achieve the development of education and culture through the image of an intellectual. An intellectual tries to explain and prove his opinions about science, technology, culture, state, and society through clear, convincing scientific evidence and expresses it beautifully. It is necessary to mention that the views of Jadids, led by M. Behbudi, regarding the development of society, education, science, technology, and culture, and the expression of their opinions about this in their works, are of great importance in the development of the science of pedagogy. In this regard, it is necessary to form the competence of working with information, i.e. media competence, in the study, analysis, and conclusion of information and data, and in this regard, our teachers organize their classes based on modern approaches and fulfill their tasks. It is important that in history classes, our teachers should effectively use interactive methods to form life skills in students through their lessons.

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